

Cosmological Model for Studying Population Dynamics

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Unlike the universe, an expanding population expands into a material environment and the amount of its mass can change. In order to capture these aspects when describing the expansion of a population, we adopt a cosmological scalar field model with particles of a variable mass. We show that the Friedmann equations from cosmology are applicable in this context as well. With the help of these equations, we examine the scale factor, $a(t)$, the density of living matter, $\rho_m(t)$, and the amount of living matter, $a^3(t)\rho_m(t)$, over time for a population.

I. INTRODUCTION

Cosmic and population phenomena exhibit interesting common features, such as expansion and clustering, which raise the question of whether there are models that describe such phenomena in both cosmology and population dynamics. In this paper, we focus our attention on the expansion of the universe and a population. In cosmology, the theory of the expansion of the cosmos (see, e.g., [1,2]) is based on the Friedmann equations, derived by Friedmann in 1922 with the help of general relativity theory. Later, it was shown that these equations can also be obtained on the basis of Newton's theory of gravitation. The question now arises as to whether this theory can also serve as a guide for a theory of population expansion. When dealing with this question, we must bear in mind fundamental differences between expansion of the universe and expansion of a population. The universe expands into a vacuum, into nothingness. A population, on the other hand, expands into an environment filled with matter. Furthermore, the amount of matter/energy in the universe remains constant, whereas in an expanding population the amount of living matter changes in general. In this paper, we choose a cosmological scalar field model (see, e.g. [3], and references therein) with particles of time-varying mass (VAMP, variable mass particle model (see, e.g. [4,5,6])). In cosmology, the scalar field represents dark energy, which, instead of a negative cosmological constant, can describe an acceleration expansion of the universe. In the VAMP scenario, matter is dark matter, which is variable over time due to its interaction with dark energy. In our analogous transfer of this scenario to population dynamics, dark matter corresponds to living matter, and dark energy to a kind of elixir of life.

II. BASIC FORMULAS, COSMOLOGICAL REFERENCE MODEL

Cosmic expansion in homogeneous and isotropic models of the universe is governed by the two Friedmann equations. These equations, derived from Einstein's field equations of gravity for the Friedmann-Lemaître-Robertson-Walker metric and a perfect fluid with given mass density ϱ and pressure p , read:

$$3H^2 = \varrho, \quad (1)$$

$$-2\dot{H} = \varrho + p, \quad (2)$$

where $H = \dot{a}/a$ is the Hubble parameter, $a(t)$ is the scale factor of the universe, and an 'over dot' stands for the differentiation with respect to the cosmic time t . Note that here and in the following, all equations are written in dimensionless form. When deriving the Friedmann equations within the framework of Newton's theory of gravity, the gravitational force of a sphere on a test particle on its surface is considered, which yields the second Friedmann equation (2), the acceleration equation. With the help of this equation and the energy conservation equation,

$$\dot{\varrho} + 3H(\varrho + p) = 0, \quad (3)$$

which results from the first law of thermodynamics, the first Friedmann equation (e.g.[1]) can be obtained.

In cosmology, scalar field models such as the quintessence model, a non-relativistic model, and the tachyon model (see, e.g., [7,8,9], and references therein), a relativistic model, have been studied for over two decades to describe interesting cosmological phenomena such as the acceleration and inflationary expansion of the universe and the interaction between dark energy and dark matter (see, e.g., [3] and references therein). As a cosmological reference model for studying population dynamics, we will use a tachyon VAMP model here.

It should be noted that the term "tachyon model" is a technical term derived from string theory, but in this model, the scalar field moves at sublight speed (cf.[10]). In our reference model [11] pressureless ($p_m = 0$) dust as dark matter, and tachyonic fluid as dark energy, represented by time varying scalar field $\phi(t)$, are the main constituents of the universe. Thus, ϱ and p are given by

$$\varrho = \varrho_m + \varrho_\phi, \quad (4)$$

$$p = p_\phi, \quad (5)$$

where ϱ_m denotes the density of dark matter, ϱ_ϕ the density of energy of the scalar field, and p_ϕ the pressure of the scalar field. For a tachyonic scalar field, ϱ_ϕ and p_ϕ are given by

$$\varrho_\phi = \frac{V(\phi)}{\sqrt{1 - \dot{\phi}^2}} \quad (6)$$

and

$$p_\phi = -V(\phi)\sqrt{1 - \dot{\phi}^2}, \quad (7)$$

where $V(\phi)$ is the potential function of the scalar field and $\dot{\phi}^2$ is the kinetic part of the scalar field. The energy conservation of the total energy/matter content of the universe takes the form

$$\dot{\varrho} + 3H(\varrho + p_\phi) = 0. \quad (8)$$

Furthermore, with Eqs.(4) and(6), the first Friedmann equation, Eq.(1), now reads

$$3H^2 = \varrho_m + \frac{V(\phi)}{\sqrt{1 - \dot{\phi}^2}}, \quad (9)$$

and with Eqs.(4) and (7), the second Friedmann equation, Eq.(2), now reads

$$-2\dot{H} = \varrho_m + \frac{V(\phi)}{\sqrt{1 - \dot{\phi}^2}} - V(\phi)\sqrt{1 - \dot{\phi}^2}. \quad (10)$$

In the VAMP scenario the matter particles depend on time t through the time varying scalar field $\phi(t)$. Since the matter particles are stable, its number density n_m must obey the following conservation equation

$$\dot{n}_m + 3Hn_m = 0. \quad (11)$$

The mass of the matter particles, denoted by Q_m , is assumed to depend on the scalar ϕ . Thus ϱ_m depends on the scalar field as follows [11]

$$\varrho_m(\phi) = Q_m(\phi)n_m. \quad (12)$$

By differentiating Eq.(12) with respect to time and using Eq.(11), for the matter one obtains the following conservation equation

$$\dot{\varrho}_m + 3H\varrho_m = -\frac{Q'_m(\phi)}{Q_m(\phi)}\dot{\phi}\varrho_m, \quad (13)$$

where the prime stands for derivative with respect to the scalar field ϕ .

Furthermore, Eqs.(8) and (13) yield the conservation equation for dark energy, ϱ_ϕ , in presence of varying mass dark matter particles

$$\dot{\varrho}_\phi + 3H(\varrho_\phi + p_\phi) = -\frac{Q'_m(\phi)}{Q_m(\phi)}\dot{\phi}\varrho_m. \quad (14)$$

From Eqs.(13) and (14) it can be seen that interaction between dark energy and dark matter is described by the term $\frac{Q'_m(\phi)}{Q_m(\phi)}\dot{\phi}\varrho_m$ on the right-hand side of Eq.(14), where $Q'_m(\phi)\dot{\phi} > 0$ indicates that there is an energy transfer from dark energy to dark matter, where $Q'_m(\phi)\dot{\phi} < 0$ indicates the opposite. Finally, using Eqs.(6),(7) and (14) one can derive the equation of motion for the tachyon field in the VAMP scenario

$$\frac{\ddot{\phi}}{1 - \dot{\phi}^2} + \frac{V'}{V} + 3H\dot{\phi} = -\frac{Q'_m(\phi)}{Q_m(\phi)}\varrho_m \frac{\sqrt{1 - \dot{\phi}^2}}{V}, \quad (15)$$

where $V' = \partial V/\partial\phi$. In our cosmological reference model [11] the mass of the dark particles is a function of scalar field ϕ as

$$Q_m(\phi) = Q_{mo} \exp(-\alpha\phi) \quad (16)$$

and the potential of the scalar field ϕ as

$$V(\phi) = V_o \exp(\beta\phi), \quad (17)$$

where Q_{mo} and V_o are constants and α and β are constant parameters.

III. POPULATION DYNAMICS WITHIN THE FRAMEWORK OF THE VAMP MODEL

In the following we will focus on the expansion of a population within the framework of the scenario outlined in Sec.II. Now the matter is living matter and the scalar field ϕ represents a kind of elixir of life. To obtain the energy balance equation, we consider a large thermally closed system with a rigid boundary and volume Ω , and a scalar field $\phi(t)$ therein. Embedded in this system is a small subsystem with volume Ω_1 , which in addition to field $\phi(t)$ contains homogeneously and isotopically distributed matter that interacts with the field. The energy E in the large system

$$E = \varrho\Omega, \quad (18)$$

where ϱ denotes the energy density in Ω , is given by

$$E = (\varrho_m + \varrho_\phi)\Omega_1 + \varrho_\phi(\Omega - \Omega_1) \quad (19)$$

where ϱ_m and ϱ_ϕ denote the density of matter and density of the scalar field, respectively. From energy conservation,

$$dE = 0, \quad (20)$$

one obtains the energy balance equation

$$\dot{\varrho} + 3H\varrho_m + \dot{\varrho}_\phi \frac{\Omega}{a^3(t)} = 0, \quad (21)$$

where

$$\frac{\dot{\Omega}_1}{\Omega_1} = 3H \quad (22)$$

has been used. Furthermore, from Eqs.(21) and (13) one obtains

$$\dot{\varrho}_\phi = -\frac{a^3(t)}{\Omega} \dot{\phi} \frac{Q'_m}{Q_m} \varrho_m. \quad (23)$$

And differentiating ϱ_ϕ from Eq.(6) with respect to the time one finds

$$\dot{\varrho}_\phi = \frac{\dot{\phi}}{\sqrt{1-\dot{\phi}^2}} \left[V' + \frac{V}{1-\dot{\phi}^2} \ddot{\phi} \right]. \quad (24)$$

Finally, from Eqs.(23) and (24) one obtains the equation of motion for the scalar field $\phi(t)$:

$$\frac{\partial V(\phi)}{\partial \phi} + \frac{V(\phi)\ddot{\phi}}{1-\dot{\phi}^2} = -\sqrt{1-\dot{\phi}^2} \frac{a^3(t)}{\Omega} \varrho_m \frac{\partial Q_m(\phi)}{\partial \phi} \frac{1}{Q_m(\phi)}. \quad (25)$$

By defining

$$p_m^{\text{eff}} = -\frac{1}{3H} \varrho_m \dot{\phi} \frac{Q_m}{Q_m} \quad (26)$$

as internal effective pressure of interaction in Ω_1 caused by the interaction of matter in Ω_1 with the scalar field, and substituting Eqs.(23) and (26) into (21), then Eq.(21) becomes

$$\dot{\varrho}_m + 3H(\varrho_m + p_m^{\text{eff}}). \quad (27)$$

Furthermore, a comparison of (27) with (3) suggests that expansion of the system Ω_1 is governed by the Friedmann equations

$$3H^2 = \varrho_m, \quad (28)$$

$$-2\dot{H} = \varrho_m + p_m^{\text{eff}}. \quad (29)$$

However, the last step of our consideration was not trivial, as it implies that the components of the living matter under consideration interact with each other with a force of the type of gravitational force. By doing so the Friedmann equations Eqs.(28) and (29) form the basis for the investigation presented below for the time dependence of $a(t)$, $\varrho_m(t)$ and $a(t)^3 \varrho_m(t)$. These same equations show that expansion of Ω_1 is not governed by ϱ_ϕ and p_ϕ , but only by ϱ_m and p_m^{eff} . This is not really surprising, since $\phi(t)$ is equally as strong inside and outside Ω_1 and therefore cannot contribute to the expansion of Ω_1 , except through p_m^{eff} . Using Friedmann's equations, Eqs.(28) and (29), the time dependence of the scale factor, $a(t)$, the density, $\varrho_m(t)$, and the amount of matter, $a^3(t)\varrho_m(t)$, can be examined, as shown in Sec.IV.

IV. TIME DEPENDENCE OF THE SCALE FACTOR AND THE DENSITY AND THE AMOUNT OF THE MATTER

The starting point is Eq. (13), which, using Eq. (23), reads as follows

$$\dot{\varrho}_m + 3H\varrho_m = -\alpha\dot{\phi}\varrho_m. \quad (30)$$

After a few simple mathematical manipulations, Eq. (30) yields the following expression for the amount of matter in subspace Ω_1

$$\varrho_m(t)a^3(t) = \varrho_m(t_0)a^3(t_0) \exp \{-\alpha [\phi(t) - \phi(t_0)]\}. \quad (31)$$

Here t_0 denotes the initial point in time of a downhill motion of the scalar field. Replacing in Eq.(31) $\varrho_m(t)$ using $3H^2$ with the help of the first Friedmann equation, Eq. (28), one obtains, after simple mathematical manipulations, the time dependence of the scale factor

$$a(t) = \left[a^{3/2}(t_0) + \frac{2}{3} \left(\frac{\varrho_m(t_0)a^3(t_0)}{3} \right)^{1/2} \int_{t_0}^t dt \exp \left\{ -\frac{\alpha}{2} [\phi(t) - \phi(t_0)] \right\} \right]^{2/3}. \quad (32)$$

Finally, the expression for $\varrho_m(t)$ can be obtained by inserting $a(t)$, Eq. (32), into Eq. (31).

To gain an idea on how the quantities of interest explicitly depend on time, let us consider the equation of motion of the scalar factor $\phi(t)$, Eq. (15), under the assumption $a^3(t)/\Omega \ll 1$ (small

times) and $\dot{\phi}^2 \ll 1$ (slow roll condition (cf., e.g. , [12], and references therein)). Then Eq. (15) reduces to

$$\ddot{\phi} = -\beta, \quad (33)$$

where β is the parameter from the potential Eq. (17).

From Eq. (33) we find

$$\phi(t) - \phi(t_0) = \dot{\phi}(t_0)(t - t_0) - \frac{1}{2}\beta(t - t_0)^2. \quad (34)$$

Accordingly, for a downhill motion of the scalar field ($\dot{\phi}(t_0) < 0$) the amount of matter increases exponentially with time.

V. CONCLUDING REMARKS

The main concern in this paper was to study whether an expanding population can also be described by the Friedmann equations, even though a population expands into a material environment and not like the universe, into a vacuum. The resulting Friedmann equations, Eqs. (28) and (29), show that, according to these equations, the expansion of a population is caused only by the density of matter and the effective pressure resulting from the interaction of the matter with the scalar field but not by the energy density of the scalar field.

In this paper we assumed that the force between the components of the living matter is similar to gravity. This assumption is essential, as our argumentation in obtaining the Friedmann equations, Eqs. (28) and (29), still contains the validity of the general theory of relativity and Newton's theory of gravity, respectively. It is not essential, as done in this paper, to describe the scalar field under consideration using a tachyon model. One could also use another scalar field model, e.g. the quintessence model. In this paper we also used the Friedmann equations, Eqs. (28) and (29), to investigate the explicit time dependence of the scale factor, $a(t)$, and the density of living matter, $\varrho_m(t)$, and the amount of living matter, $a^3(t)\varrho_m(t)$. The main aim was to gain insight into the general course of the time dependence of these quantities. To this end we made rough approximations that seem appropriate at the given current state of our theory. A more realistic, more sophisticated theory would probably require a more precise careful analysis of the time dependence, such as an analysis within the framework of autonomous differential equation systems (see, e.g., [11]).

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